

Efficacy of Labour Analgesia with Standard Epidural versus Dural Puncture Epidural Techniques in Parturients – A Randomized Control Trial

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Abstract:

Introduction: Neuraxial analgesia has a minimal risk of side effects and is very effective, making it the gold standard of labor analgesia. If the dural puncture epidural method (DPE) can validate midline implantation and increase intrathecal translocation of epidural medicines, it might enhance the quality of analgesia. The current research set out to evaluate the relative merits of standard epidural and dural puncture epidural approach for labor analgesia.

Material and Methods: Sixty-four full term primi or multiparous parturients were randomly allocated to standard epidural technique (group 1, n=32) and dural puncture epidural technique (group 2, n=32) managed with dural puncture using 26-gauge Whitacre needle through the 18 G Tuohy needle. Visual analogue scale, hemodynamic variables, onset of analgesia, details of sensory and motor block by Bromage scale, and adverse events were noted and analysed.

Results: The duration to achieve adequate analgesia was 12.02±1.98 in group 1 and 10.46±2.22 in group 2. Duration to achieve complete sacral spread was 17.18±4.89 in group 1 and 16.64±3.90 in group 2. VAS score <10 at 10 minutes was observed in 59.38% of cases in group 1 and 65.62% in group 2. Spontaneous vaginal deliveries are more common, and no significant changes in the hemodynamic parameters.

Conclusion: Dural puncture epidural technique and standard epidural technique are efficacious, however, DPE improves sacral spread, fasten the onset of analgesia, and bilateral pain relief in parturients.

Keywords: Labor analgesia, Ropivacaine, Dexmedetomidine, VAS score, dural puncture epidural technique.

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Introduction

Neuraxial analgesia is the most effective method for alleviating labor pain. While there are numerous pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic alternatives for alleviating labor pain, neuraxial analgesia continues to be the most effective [1]. Dural puncture epidural or combined spinal-epidural techniques like initiation approaches may provide some benefits over regular epidural insertion [2].

Over the past few decades, neuraxial techniques have undergone a significant transformation, enabling the safe and effective administration of labor neuraxial analgesia to foetus and mother. As a result, neuraxial analgesia is becoming a more frequently requested and implemented method for the provision of labor analgesia [3]. The DPE method is comparable to the combined spinal-

epidural procedure, but does not include the administration of intrathecal medications. Studies have shown that DPE had a little faster onset of analgesia, greater sacral coverage, lower rate of motor block and a lower incidence of unilateral block than the epidural method [4]. Chau et al. found that the combined spinal-epidural approach was more successful than DPE and conventional epidural procedure. Furthermore, DPE was linked with few adverse effects such as pruritis, maternal hypotension, and uterine hypertonus compared to CSE [5].

The potency of DPE technique is most likely dependent on using a 25-G or bigger spinal needle. According to Bernads CM et al., the quantity of local anaesthetic flow across the dura is depending

on the size of the dural puncture, and puncture with a 24-G Sprotte needle was substantially more effective than a 27-G Whitacre needle [6]. Thomas et al. discovered that puncturing the dura with a 27-G needle as part of a DPE did not enhance pain relief when compared to a normal epidural [7]. With the availability of limited literature in the current study settings this study was designed to evaluate the efficacy of labor analgesia with dural puncture epidural versus conventional epidural technique.

Material and Methods

This prospective, randomized, single blinded study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology in association with Department of Obstetrics and gynaecology at Osmania Medical College and Hospital, Hyderabad and Government Medical College, Nagarkurnool from January 2023 to March 2024. A total of 64 pregnant women between 21-35 years of age, with term labor of primi and secondary gravida, ASA grade I and II, cases with active labor with cervical dilation of 2-3 cm, cases requested labor analgesia and cases willing to participate were included. Cases with VAS score below 50 mm during active contraction, with gravida 3 and above, contraindication to neuraxial anaesthesia history of caesarean section, allergy to local anaesthetics, history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, severe anaemia, cardiovascular complication, renal diseases, neurological complications, obesity, with antepartum haemorrhage and not willing to

participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all the study participants and family members. The study proposal was reviewed and approved by institutional ethics committee.

Study participants were randomly divided into two groups. Group 1 cases were managed with traditional epidural technique without dural puncture and group 2 cases were managed with dural puncture using 26-gauge Whitacre needle through the 18 G Tuohy needle. All the parturients were undergone preanesthetic check-up. Baseline hemodynamic parameters, and oxygen saturation were recorded. Neuraxial procedure was performed at L3-L4 level in sitting position and dural puncture epidural technique was performed. Both study groups received epidural bolus of 0.125% bupivacaine with 50 mcg fentanyl in 4 ml for 3 minutes followed by infusion of 0.1% bupivacaine with 2 mcg/ml fentanyl for every 90 minutes. Details of onset of analgesia, details of sensory and motor blockade (modified bromage score) and maximum dermatomal levels were recorded. Postoperative pain was assessed by visual analog score and adverse events were monitored up to 48 hours. Collected data was analysed by using SPSS 23.0. Categorical variables were represented in frequency and percentage. ANOVA was used to be used to compare the groups. $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant outcome.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of study participants.

Parameters	Group 1 (n=32)		Group 2 (n=32)		Chi-square value	p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage		
Age (In years)						
21-25	15	46.88%	17	53.12%	0.284	1.053
26-30	13	40.62%	11	34.37%		
31-35	04	12.5%	04	12.5%		
Weight (Mean \pm SD)	62.30 \pm 6.21		63.66 \pm 5.98		0.475	0.041
Height	159.4 \pm 2.37		160.2 \pm 3.14		0.197	0.063
BMI (Kg/m²)						
<25	27	84.37%	25	7.81%	0.378	0.0219
>25	05	15.62%	07	21.87%		
Parity						
Primi	20	62.5%	18	56.25%	0.310	0.056
Multi	12	37.5%	14	43.75%		
Cervical dilation	4.39 \pm 0.68		4.28 \pm 0.54			1.652

The majority participants were between 21-25 years. The cervical dilation at the time of procedure was comparative high in group 2 (4.28) than group 1 (4.39) (Table 1).

The duration to achieve adequate analgesia, and mean block bromage score level at 20 min was comparatively high in group 1 than group 2 ($p < 0.05$). The duration to achieve complete sacral

spread was 17.18 in group 1 and 16.64 in group 2 ($p > 0.05$). VAS score < 10 at 10 minutes was observed in 59.38% of cases in group 1 and 65.62% in group 2.

Cases with unequal blocks was 31.25% and 15.62% and bilateral sensory block at 20 minutes was observed in 59.37% and 40.62% of cases in group 1 and group 2 respectively. The motor block

at 20 minutes using bromage scale was 2.77 in group 1 and 2.51 in group 2 (Table 2).

Table 2: Details of block characteristics and VAS score.

Parameters	Group 1 (n=32)	Group 2 (n=32)
	Mean ± SD/ n (%)	Mean ± SD/ n (%)
Duration to achieve adequate analgesia	12.02±1.98	10.46±2.22
Duration to achieve complete sacral spread	17.18±4.89	16.64±3.90
Cases with VAS score <10 at 10 min	19 (59.38%)	21 (65.62%)
Participants with unequal blocks	10 (31.25%)	05 (15.62%)
Bromage scale using motor block at 20 min	2.77±0.41	2.51±0.63
Bilateral sensory block at 20 min	19 (59.37%)	13 (40.62%)

Graph 1: Mean systolic blood pressure among the study groups.

The mean systolic blood pressure was significantly low in group 2 from beginning to 20 min after the procedure. The mean diastolic blood pressure high at baseline in group 2 then showed gradual

decrease till 20 minutes after procedure (Graph 1 & 2). Normal vaginal deliveries was commonly seen in both study groups followed by caesarean deliveries (Graph 3).

Graph 2: Mean diastolic blood pressure among the study groups.

Graph 3: Details of mode of delivery among the study groups.

Table 3: Adverse events reported among the study participants.

Parameters	Group 1		Group 2	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Post dural puncture headache	-	-	01	3.12%
Nausea/vomiting	02	6.25%	02	6.26%
Pruritus	02	6.25%	-	-
Foetal bradycardia	01	3.12%	-	-
Hypotension	01	3.12%	-	-
Shivering	02	6.25%	01	3.12%

Discussion

Spinal epidural and epidural alone are the standard methods of labor analgesia. Dural-puncture

epidural (DPE) is a popular kind of neuraxial labor analgesia for labor pain alleviation due to its high effectiveness and minimal risk of unwanted effects [8-10]. This study was compared the efficacy of labor analgesia with dural puncture epidural versus conventional epidural technique.

Pritam Y et al. randomly divided 60 term primigravida parturients with ASA grades I and II into two groups of 30: conventional epidural (group E) and dural puncture epidural (group DE). In group DE, 60 subjects had enough analgesia after 5 minutes, but none in group E did ($P < 0.05$). At 5 minutes, group E had a mean VAS score of 4.97, compared to group DE's 4.33 ($P < 0.05$). The duration of analgesia after the first bolus dosage was 99.37 minutes in group E and 98.77 minutes in group DE ($P > 0.05$). There was no significant change in haemodynamic parameters between the two study groups [11]. Hon Sen Tan et al. discovered no statistically significant differences in primary composite outcomes between the dural puncture and standard epidural groups in 141 obese parturients. The research results did not support regular dural puncture epidural use in obese parturients, and there was no statistically significant difference in analgesic quality between study groups [12]. Cappiello et al. found a decrease in VAS ratings after 20 minutes in the DPE group, but no change in VAS levels before or after 20 minutes of analgesia onset [13]. Similarly, the majority of patients in both research groups had a lower VAS score 10 minutes after the surgery (59.38% in group 1 and 65.62% in group 2). A meta-analysis from 2022 found that women using DPE labor analgesia had quicker onset to adequate pain relief, with no related maternal or foetal adverse effects [14]. In a study involving 150 pregnant women, Rao WY et al. randomly assigned some to receive DPE, epidural anaesthesia alone (EA) or combine spinal-epidural anaesthesia (CSE). The results showed that DPE had better block quality and a quicker onset than EA, and it had less of an impact on maternal hemodynamic parameters than CSE. According to these results, the dural puncture is a key component of the DPE technique of labor analgesia transmitted to CS, and it also plays a role in increasing the effectiveness of epidural top-ups during CSE anesthesia [15]. Prospective randomized single-blind research by Pažur I et al. found no statistical significance in the numerical pain rating scale after 10 minutes. The study included 76 parturients randomly allocated to either the regular epidural or DPE method group. However, 97.4% of individuals in the dural puncture epidural group reported satisfactory analgesia after 10 minutes. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of number of additional boluses, time to delivery, Bromage scale achieved, or maternal outcomes [16]. In a study conducted by

Yadav P et al., it was shown that parturients in the DPE group were more likely to get appropriate analgesia between 5 and 10 minutes compared to the conventional epidural method group [17].

These inconsistent findings might be attributed to methodological variability. The processes controlling the flow of local anesthetics via the meninges and the hole generated by the dural puncture are complicated and have yet to be completely understood [18,19]. The size of the dural puncture is significant, but there are likely additional aspects to consider, such as the total drug mass of the injectate, the time since DPE, epidural bolus delivery, and injectate pressure created.

Similarly, in this study, neither approach caused any adverse outcomes for the parturients, such as cardiovascular catastrophes, complete spinal, unintentional dura puncture, or catheter kinking. Complications such as nausea, pruritus, headache, foetal bradycardia, hypotension, and method of delivery were similar across the two groups, with no statistically significant difference (Table 3). Further studies should focus on spinal needles with different gauges for an optimal dural puncture with dural puncture epidural technique for labor analgesia.

Conclusion

The duration to produce appropriate analgesia is shorter in the dural puncture epidural technique compared to standard epidural technique. Although dural puncture epidural improves sacral spread, onset of analgesia, and bilateral pain relief in laboring women, both traditional epidural and dural puncture epidural techniques have improved block quality with very few maternal and foetal side effects and no negative impact on mode of delivery.

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